

Highlights

Operation, control and assessment of a full-scale membrane distillation unit for treating desalination brine in the context of greenhouse production

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- Results in a full-scale V-AGMD unit treating reverse osmosis brine are reported.
- Biomass heat used for the first time to power a full-scale MD unit.
- Cooling limitations turn vacuum assistance ineffective to improve vapor flux.
- A regulatory control architecture is validated to maintain the operating conditions.
- V-AGMD can take part of a water grid for a sustainable agricultural activity.

Operation, control and assessment of a full-scale membrane distillation unit for treating desalination brine in the context of greenhouse production

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Abstract

Membrane distillation (MD) is a thermal desalination technology with a niche application in the concentration of brines. This paper aims to assess the operation, control, and performance of the largest full-scale vacuum-assisted air-gap membrane distillation (V-AGMD) system reported to date in the literature, using biomass heat as thermal source and real brine from a reverse osmosis unit with salinity 63.7 g L^{-1} as feed. The levelized cost of water of a large-scale V-AGMD plant has been estimated using experimental results. The MD unit comprises up to ten multi-envelope air-gap modules, and is installed in the facilities of the AgroConnect project at IFAPA, an agricultural research centre close to the University of Almería (Spain). Results show that cooling limitations in the V-AGMD operation cancel out the beneficial effect of vacuum assistance on vapor diffusion, especially when the feed temperature and the feed flow rate are increased, hindering the condensation, and hence reducing the permeate productivity even down to 40 % in comparison with conventional AGMD operation. This work demonstrates that full-scale V-AGMD can take part in a future optimized sustainable water network to supply water for intensive agricultural activity in the south-east of Spain, although a sufficient cooling supply is mandatory to avoid operational issues.

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1. Introduction

The scarcity of suitable freshwater for human activity is one of the most critical challenges nowadays throughout the world, as it is a major threat to economic growth, food security, and the conservation of ecosystems [1]. Its impact on society is the main subject of study by international organizations [2]. In the particular case of Spain, around 41 % of its territory is in a state of water emergency [3], especially in the south-east of the country. Due to that, the sustainability of the growing intensive agricultural activity in semiarid or arid regions such as Andalusia, where it is a critical sector, is severely threatened. In practice, agriculture represents about 70 % of the total consumption of freshwater [4], with an expected annual increase of 1.3 % due to the expansion of the irrigated land area. In addition, this activity contributes 6.5 % to the gross domestic product and employs about 9 % of the population in this region [5].

Intensive agriculture based on greenhouses is dominant among others because of its favorable techno-economic performance. The largest accumulation of these facilities in the world (more than 32000 *Ha*) is located in Almería, one of the most arid regions in Spain, with severe problems of freshwater availability. Approximately 80 % of agricultural products are exported, which means 2700 *M€*, plus 1300 *M€* coming from the auxiliary industries [6]. These figures bring to light the need to develop efficient processes to obtain freshwater.

Desalination is increasingly implemented as a solution to obtain freshwater from seawater or inland saline sources [7]. It is a highly mature technique at an industrial scale [8], which produces around $10^8 \text{ m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$ worldwide. However, such production requires high energy consumption, potentially entailing annual emissions of around 10^8 tons CO_2 into the atmosphere, which can contribute noticeably to global warming [9]. In this sense, the use of renewable energies in desalination is a must to increase its sustainability, although so far less than 1 % of the desalination worldwide is powered by any renewable source [10]. In addition, different plans are suggested to valorize brines in the context of circular economy. These are based on concentrating

33 the brines to reduce their volume as much as possible and facilitate the sub-
34 sequent operations of crystallization. However, reverse osmosis (RO), which
35 is the most efficient desalination technology in the industry to date, does not
36 tolerate salinities much higher than $60 - 65 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ due to the excessively high
37 osmotic pressure of the feed [11, 12]. In this context, thermal desalination
38 operations have a significant advantage because the vapor pressure is much
39 less influenced by salinity than the osmotic pressure [13].

40 A thermal desalination technology that has shown great progression in
41 the last two decades in terms of upscaling is membrane distillation (MD)[14].
42 This is a nonisothermal process based on the separation of water vapor from
43 the saline feed by a hydrophobic microporous membrane. The process is
44 driven by the vapor pressure gradient generated as a consequence of a temper-
45 ature difference established between both sides of the aforementioned mem-
46 brane [15, 16]. Several authors have demonstrated the feasibility of powering
47 MD with low-grade heat sources such as solar energy or waste heat [17, 18],
48 suggesting a promising outlook for the development of greener desalination
49 processes at an affordable cost [19, 20].

50 Since the early 2010s, different commercial MD prototypes and pilot-scale
51 units have been evaluated, resulting in a wide diversity of performance results
52 [21]. Among them, multi-envelope spiral-wound MD modules with internal
53 heat recovery are the best-performing up to date. That heat recovery cons-
54 sists of using the latent heat of condensation of the vapor passing through the
55 pores of the membrane to preheat the feed that circulates on the cooling side
56 of the membrane, which reduces external thermal energy needs and there-
57 fore costs [22]. The performance of MD systems is commonly described by
58 three parameters: permeate productivity ($PFlux [\text{L h}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}]$), which is the
59 volume of permeate produced per time and membrane area, specific thermal
60 energy consumption ($STEC [\text{kWh}_{th} \text{m}^{-3}]$), indicating the amount of energy
61 required to produce 1 m^3 of permeate, and gained output ratio ($GOR [-]$),
62 which is a dimensionless parameter quantifying the number of times that the
63 external thermal energy supplied is recovered in the MD module to produce
64 more permeate.

65 The first spiral wound permeate-gap prototypes (PGMD), developed by
66 Fraunhofer ISE, were evaluated in different demonstration facilities around
67 the world, reaching $PFlux$ of $2.1 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$ and GOR of 3.8, equivalent
68 to $STEC$ of $170 \text{ kWh}_{th} \text{m}^{-3}$. However, results also showed a trade-off be-
69 tween thermal efficiency and permeate productivity, strongly influenced by
70 the residence time of the feed inside the module. This drawback leads to low

71 permeate production in a thermally efficient operation [23, 24]. A solution
 72 to mitigate the negative effect of the trade-off is to increase the membrane
 73 area without increasing the feed velocity [25]. Nevertheless, putting this
 74 strategy into practice in single envelope spiral wound MD modules was not
 75 possible without reaching an excessive pressure drop that is prone to damage
 76 the membrane. Multi-envelope air gap (AGMD) modules manufactured by
 77 the Dutch company Aquastill BV with between 12 and 24 internal channels
 78 meant progress in this sense because performance figures were double than
 79 those obtained with single envelope ones: $PFlux$ up to $4.1 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$ in the
 80 module with shorter channels (1.5 m each) and GOR up to 6.5 (equivalent
 81 to $STEC$ of $100 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$) in the module with longer channels (5 m each)
 82 [23, 26]. Commercial-scale units with several multi-envelope AGMD modules
 83 have also been put in operation. Lee et al. [27] evaluated a unit with six
 84 modules operating in parallel for the desalination of real Korean seawater.
 85 Each module had 24 internal channels of length 2.7 m and the total mem-
 86 brane area was $155.5 m^2$. The limit values of $PFlux$, $STEC$ and GOR were
 87 $1.15 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$, $170 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$ and 3.8, respectively. Soon after, three of
 88 those modules were also operated in parallel by Duong et al. [28] on a Viet-
 89 namese island to produce potable water for its inhabitants. As a consequence
 90 of the trade-off between productivity and energy efficiency, reducing the feed
 91 flow rate 2.2-fold compared to Lee et al. meant that $STEC$ was reduced
 92 down to $87 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$ ($GOR = 8$), but at the expense of producing half the
 93 permeate than with Lee’s system.

94 A new progress in reducing the specific thermal consumption of MD was
 95 made by applying vacuum inside the multi-envelope modules. Previous stud-
 96 ies on a lab scale [29–31] and bench scale [22] demonstrated that removing
 97 air from the gap of AGMD modules speeds up vapor diffusion through mem-
 98 brane pores, increasing the recovery ratio per pass in the MD module and
 99 thus its permeate productivity. Andrés-Mañas et al. [32] published the first
 100 experimental paper on the use of vacuum in spiral wound multi-envelope
 101 AGMD modules with different number and length of internal circulation
 102 channels, installed in a pilot unit in the solar desalination facilities of the
 103 Living Lab “Sustainable Desalination”, developed at CIEMAT – Plataforma
 104 Solar de Almería (Spain). The authors found that vacuum-assisted AGMD
 105 operation (V-AGMD) is the most energy efficient to date, especially for the
 106 treatment of concentrated saline solutions. Improvements of up to 234 %
 107 in $PFlux$ and up to 68 % in $STEC$ were found [33], in relation to AGMD
 108 operation without vacuum assistance [23, 26, 34]. The best experimental

109 values of the key performance parameters $PFlux$ and $STEC$ obtained so
110 far in pilot-scale MD with these multi-envelope modules were $8.7 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$
111 and $40 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$ ($GOR = 16.4$), respectively [35]. These extreme figures
112 reached with multi-envelope modules were even better than those previously
113 obtained in the desalination of real Mediterranean seawater using a vacuum
114 multi-effect MD (VMEMD) unit powered with solar energy [36, 37].

115 As it is independent of the osmotic pressure of the saline feed, the toler-
116 ance of MD to salinity is much higher than that of RO [16]. This gives MD
117 opportunities to be used in the concentration of brines coming from industrial
118 RO plants, with two main benefits: i) the possibility of developing a circular
119 economy model around the recovery of valuable marine salts and high-value
120 metals, and ii) the protection of marine ecosystems against inappropriate
121 disposal of those brines. Regarding pilot-scale MD, Gil et al. [38] evaluated
122 experimentally and modeled the steady-state brine treatment operation in a
123 PGMD module manufactured by the German company SolarSpring GmbH
124 (a spin-off of Fraunhofer ISE), powered with solar energy and placed in the
125 Living Lab “Sustainable Desalination” at CIEMAT – Plataforma Solar de
126 Almería. Values of $PFlux = 1.56 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$ and $STEC = 258 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$
127 ($GOR = 2.5$) were achieved when treating synthetic brines with salinity
128 $60 g L^{-1}$. Later, the same solar desalination system was evaluated for the con-
129 centration of synthetic brine from 65 to $140 g L^{-1}$ using a batch strategy [39].
130 On the other hand, Bindels et al. [40] assessed the ability of multi-envelope
131 modules operated in steady-state V-AGMD mode to treat a real brine from
132 an RO desalination plant close to the Mediterranean Sea with concentration
133 $65 g L^{-1}$. With no additional treatments, figures of $PFlux = 4.0 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$
134 and $GOR = 8.5$ ($STEC = 77 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$) were attained, and no signs of
135 scaling or membrane wetting were observed.

136 According to previous results, the combination of RO and MD is a suit-
137 able solution to maximize freshwater production, making the most of the
138 brines that the former technology cannot deal with, and thus contributing to
139 reach zero-liquid discharge. Although brine concentration at pilot scale has
140 previously been evaluated and modeled for multi-envelope V-AGMD mod-
141 ules with advanced heat recovery [32, 41], the use of biomass heat as thermal
142 source in MD at a commercial scale has not been tested so far. Therefore,
143 the main aim of this paper is to cover the lack of information in this field. In
144 addition, the opportunity to analyze the importance of cooling in MD arises
145 in this work. Different cooling solutions have been tested in MD systems
146 to improve the performance. The use of semi-infinite water sources such as

147 the sea or wells has been assessed. Although this is, in theory, the most
148 energy-efficient solution, the performance of the MD unit could be strongly
149 influenced by seasonal temperature changes. This issue was thoroughly de-
150 scribed by Andrés-Mañas et al. [36], who reported even 40 % less permeate
151 productivity in summer than in winter when operating a solar VMEMD unit
152 cooled with real Mediterranean seawater. Kabeel et al. [42] studied the
153 coupling of an evaporative chiller to a solar MD system and obtained 1.25
154 times more permeate than in experiments without it. Subsequently, Khalifa
155 et al. [43] implemented an air-cooled bubble column dehumidifier to cool
156 a sweeping gas MD unit. Improvements between 40 and 100 % in perme-
157 ate productivity were found, although with maximum air speed of 8 m s^{-1} ,
158 which could lead to unaffordable operating costs. In the case of commercial-
159 scale V-AGMD units, Bindels et al. [44] considered the use of a heat pump
160 as cooling source, especially in cases in which other cooling water sources
161 are unaffordable. More recently, Ayou et al. [45] simulated the coupling
162 of a solar-powered absorption heat pump to a commercial-scale V-AGMD
163 unit used to concentrate brines from RO and estimated that it is possible to
164 maintain a cooling fluid temperature of $16 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using 67 % of the produced
165 cooling capacity.

166 Within the framework of the AgroConnect project (www.agroconnect.es),
167 the performance of a V-AGMD system has been evaluated for the treatment
168 of brine coming from an RO system connected in series to the MD unit,
169 and used to provide freshwater to the experimental greenhouse placed in the
170 facilities of the IFAPA Research Center, near the University of Almería [46].
171 The novelties introduced with this work are the following:

- 172 • The V-AGMD unit operated in this study is the biggest ever reported
173 in literature, with five commercial-scale modules operating in parallel
174 (see Section 2.1).
- 175 • The multi-envelope MD modules operated have demonstrated the best
176 performance in the treatment of hypersaline water sources at pilot-scale
177 [32]. However, the brine treatment operation using full scale V-AGMD
178 has not yet been reported in the literature. Assessment of the upscaled
179 technology is a must for its future implementation in a zero-liquid dis-
180 charge process.
- 181 • The use of heat from a biomass boiler means an opportunity to power
182 the full-scale V-AGMD unit as CO_2 from the flue gases of the com-

183 bustion of vegetal waste is simultaneously supplied to the crops in the
184 experimental greenhouse itself, valorizing thus that residue. Moreover,
185 freshwater recovered from the brine in the V-AGMD unit will be avail-
186 able for irrigation, increasing the sustainability of intensive agriculture.

- 187 • The real environment in which the V-AGMD unit has been operated al-
188 lows to extend the assessment of the system beyond the ideal conditions
189 fixed at lab- or pilot-scale, which could be hard or impossible to main-
190 tain outdoors. This has provided novel information on the performance
191 of commercial-scale MD under limitations of cooling and heating.

192 The operation of the V-AGMD unit had the aim of evaluating these novel
193 aspects and establishing the convenient operational ranges under these limi-
194 tations. Steady-state experiments were carried out to facilitate the quanti-
195 fication of the performance parameters of the system with different operating
196 conditions, rather than in unsteady state operation, i.e. with feed concentra-
197 tion. A preliminary cost analysis was also performed to estimate the levelized
198 cost of water in the facility.

199 The results of this work are therefore a necessary starting point to achieve
200 the objectives of the AgroConnect project, contributing to the future devel-
201 opment, implementation, validation, and techno-economic optimization of an
202 integral water supply grid focused on covering the water needs that inten-
203 sive agricultural activity in the south-east of Spain requires, using renewable
204 energy sources and thus minimizing environmental harm.

205 The paper is organized into the following sections. Firstly, Section 2
206 provides a description of the facilities and an outline of the experimental
207 procedure followed, including the mathematical expressions of the key per-
208 formance parameters considered. Secondly, Section 3 presents results and
209 discussion of the calculated control architectures, the characterization of the
210 performance of the full-scale MD unit, and the estimations of the levelized
211 cost of water made for different experimental cases. Finally, conclusions of
212 the work and future outlook are given in Section 4.

213 **2. Materials and methods**

214 *2.1. Description of the facilities*

215 The facilities in the framework of the AgroConnect project [47] are lo-
216 cated at IFAPA, an agricultural research center close to the University of

217 Almería, in the south-east of Spain. This is a cutting-edge scientific test bed
218 which includes a fully equipped greenhouse with 1900 m^2 area, connected
219 to electrical and thermal energy supply for heating and cooling systems (in-
220 cluding the use of renewable energy sources), the generation and reuse of
221 CO_2 and the generation of water. AgroConnect is focused on developing an
222 integral water grid that will be finally used in intensive agricultural activity
223 based on greenhouses, which is the main economic engine of the province of
224 Almería. Concretely, two desalination systems connected in series have been
225 operated in these facilities to treat water from a beach well and generate
226 freshwater. The first is based on RO and was thoroughly modeled in [46],
227 and the second is based on MD and was evaluated in the present study.

228 2.1.1. Full-scale V-AGMD desalination unit

229 The full-scale MD plant (Figure 1) has a feedwater capacity of $3\text{ m}^3\text{ h}^{-1}$
230 and uses the rejected brine of the RO unit as feed. The RO unit at IFAPA has
231 a capacity of $11\text{ m}^3\text{ day}^{-1}$ permeate water and is fed directly with seawater
232 from a nearby beach well [46]. The permeate water is stored in a 100 m^3 tank,
233 while the residual brine (about $22\text{ m}^3\text{ day}^{-1}$) is stored in a 50-m^3 reservoir
234 tank and then used to feed the MD unit. The main advantage of MD com-
235 pared to RO is the ability of the former to treat high-concentrated solutions
236 that RO cannot handle, thus improving overall freshwater production.

Figure 1: Full-scale MD desalination unit.

237 The MD unit consists of a supporting frame which accommodates all
 238 the required piping and instrumentation, the feed tanks, the permeate tank,
 239 the heating and cooling heat exchangers, and ten commercial-scale advanced
 240 multi-envelope MD modules named AS26 and manufactured by the Dutch
 241 company Aquastill. Only five of these modules have been operated in parallel
 242 so far due to limitations in heating supply. Each module has a spiral wound
 243 arrangement with 25.92 m^2 membrane area, made of PE without backing,
 244 $0.32 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ pore diameter, and 85 % porosity. PP spacers delimit 24 air gaps
 245 and 24 internal channels: 12 in the evaporation side of the membrane (that is,
 246 evaporation channels) and 12 in the cooling side (that is, cooling channels).
 247 Further details on the internal features of the module can be found by the
 248 reader in [32].

249 Figure 2 shows the connectivity diagram of the V-AGMD unit. Each
 250 module is connected to the rest of the unit by means of five pipes. Two are
 251 the inlets of the evaporation and cooling channels, and the other two are
 252 the corresponding outlets. Temperature sensors, flowmeters, and pressure
 253 transmitters are installed to verify that the operation is performed in the
 254 correct ranges. The fifth pipe carries the permeate to the permeate tank and
 255 includes an electrical conductivity meter to check the permeate quality.

Figure 2: Schematic of the commercial-scale MD unit.

256 Two separated circuits supply heat and cooling to the MD unit, including
257 a plate-and-frame titanium heat exchanger each. On one hand, the heating
258 circuit supplies thermal energy continuously from a biomass boiler (see sec-
259 tion 2.1.2) to the preheated feed leaving the cooling channels of the modules
260 at temperature TCO , to heat it up around the hot temperature setpoint
261 TEI . A 3-way valve V_2 allows maintaining that setpoint by regulating the
262 thermal fluid flow rate in the heat exchanger. On the other hand, the cooling
263 circuit dissipates the excess of heat in the feed with another plate-and-frame
264 heat exchanger to improve the condensation of vapor, since the feed is used as
265 coolant inside the modules. By means of another 3-way valve, V_1 , the cooling
266 water flow rate is regulated to maintain a temperature around the setpoint
267 TCI before entering the cooling channels of the MD modules. Moreover, the
268 internal flow rates (FFR_1 and FFR_2) of the MD module are also controlled
269 by manipulating the pumps' frequencies 1 and 2.

270 The unit has been operated in AGMD and in V-AGMD mode to per-
271 form a further assessment. Vacuum level is adjusted with a manual relief
272 valve, from atmospheric pressure (conventional AGMD) to approximately
273 150 *mbar abs*, high enough not to influence the vapor condensation process
274 or the permeate quality, maintaining salt rejection factors above 99 % in all
275 experiments performed [48].

276 2.1.2. Biomass boiler

277 A biomass boiler (Figure 3) with nominal thermal power 160 kW_{th} is
278 used to steadily supply heat to the MD operation. The heat generated in the
279 combustion of vegetable pellets from the experimental greenhouse at IFAPA
280 is delivered to the water in an external heating circuit, connected to the
281 corresponding heat exchanger of the MD unit. Furthermore, the flue gases
282 are then filtered and recycled in the experimental greenhouse as source of
283 CO_2 to improve the photosynthesis of crops [49].

284 2.1.3. Cooling and vacuum circuit

285 The closed-loop cooling system includes a 1500- L water tank, a flow reg-
286 ulation valve (V_1), and a centrifugal pump with power 3 kW_{el} . Vacuum in
287 the internal gaps of the five modules and in the permeate tank is generated
288 by Venturi effect with negligible additional energy consumption, making the
289 most of the suction force of that pump in eight narrowing tubes placed also
290 into the cooling circuit. The volume of water in the tank is enough to buffer
291 large temperature differences during the experiments but is subject to the

Figure 3: Biomass boiler used to supply heat to the MD unit.

292 ambient temperature in each case due to the absence of cooling devices in
293 the facility.

294 2.2. Experimental procedure

295 The experimental campaign carried out in this work with the commercial-
296 scale MD unit comprised 16 steady-state experiments combining different
297 values of the inputs TEI and FFR , each one replicated for improving the
298 accuracy of the results. Concretely, the setpoints for TEI were 60, 65, and
299 70 °C, whereas for FFR , 4000, 6000, and 7000 $L h^{-1}$ were used (i.e., 800,
300 1200, and 1400 $L h^{-1}$ per operating module). These values are in the range
301 of those used in previous studies with multi-envelope modules similar to
302 those installed in the unit assessed in the present work, avoiding thus the
303 risk of module damage due to excessive hydraulic pressure or temperature
304 [25, 41]. It is worth mentioning that multi-envelope modules tolerate TEI up
305 to 80 °C, but temperatures above 70 °C could not be tested due to the lim-
306 itation of the biomass boiler power. Instantaneous values of TEI and FFR
307 were electronically regulated by a programmable logic controller (PLC) to be
308 kept as close to the setpoints as possible during the entire operational time.
309 Maximum deviations for TEI and FFR were 2.9 °C and 300 $L h^{-1}$, respec-

310 tively. Additionally, the PLC recorded the operational variables necessary to
311 calculate the key performance parameters (see Section 2.4).

312 The temperature TCI was not regulated during the operation, although a
313 maximum of $3\text{ }^{\circ}C$ over the setpoint was tolerated. Cooling water was taken
314 from a 1000- L buffer tank, which was kept outdoors, exposed to ambient
315 temperature to expand the scope of the characterization to different seasons.
316 The real brine from the RO unit was the feed used for the experiments
317 in the MD unit, with salinity $S = 63.7 \pm 3.1\text{ }g\text{ }L^{-1}$. The feed of the RO
318 plant came, in turn, from natural water in a beach well near the IFAPA
319 research facilities. The feed salinity was maintained constant throughout the
320 experiments because the permeate was returned to the primary feed tank of
321 the MD unit.

322 Each experiment started when the temperatures and flow rates were kept
323 steady and as close to the fixed setpoints as possible. A minimum duration of
324 1 h was established to collect sufficient data to ensure a reliable estimation
325 of the key MD parameters. To start a run, the feed is pumped from the
326 primary feed tank with flow rate FFR through a plate-and-frame HX, where
327 it is cooled to temperature TCI by means of water in the external cooling
328 circuit, the flow rate of which is regulated by the valve V_1 . The suction
329 force of the pump in the cooling circuit is used in eight narrowing tubes to
330 generate vacuum by Venturi effect. This leads to an absolute pressure inside
331 the modules as low as 150 $mbar\ abs$, which is kept constant throughout the
332 experimental campaign, regulating minor changes with a manual relief valve.
333 This valve was fully opened to operate in conventional AGMD mode.

334 The cooled feed enters the cooling channels of the MD modules after-
335 wards and is preheated by the latent heat of condensation of the vapor as
336 it advances through them. The five modules work in parallel, each treating
337 a fifth of the total circulating feed flow. The preheated feed exits the mod-
338 ules to a secondary feed tank, which is used as a buffer to avoid excessive
339 hydraulic pressure drop inside the modules and the pipes. Before reentering
340 the modules, the feed is reheated from TCO to TEI using external heat
341 from the biomass boiler in another plate and frame HX. The flow of heat-
342 ing water in the boiler circuit is regulated by the valve V_2 . As the hot feed
343 circulates through the evaporation channels and countercurrent to the liquid
344 in the cooling ones, vapor passes through the membrane pores fostered by
345 the reduced absolute pressure inside the gaps of the modules and is then
346 condensed onto the foils that form the walls of the cooling channels. The
347 latent heat of condensation is then delivered to the feed circulating through

348 the cooling channels, preheating it without additional heat supply. The brine
349 is continuously returned to the primary feed tank after passing through the
350 modules, while the permeate is returned by the system automatically and
351 intermittently, whenever 7 liters are produced. Therefore, variations in the
352 volume and concentration of the feed are negligible, thus maintaining the
353 steady state at every moment. The permeate quality is frequently controlled
354 by measurements of its electrical conductivity. No notable variations in that
355 parameter were observed during the experimental campaign, maintaining salt
356 rejection factors above 99 %.

357 2.3. Controllers

358 To control the activities of the feed pumps associated with the frequencies
359 F_1 and F_2 of pumps 1 and 2, respectively, and of the regulatory valves V_1
360 and V_2 (see Figure 2), ideal structure proportional integral (PI) controllers
361 were designed for each system. The use of the PI structure is due to the fact
362 that only two design premises are required in this control scheme, such as
363 zero steady-state error and a desired closed-loop time constant. Moreover,
364 the systems to be controlled are described by first-order transfer functions.
365 Another advantage is that these controllers, the transfer function of which
366 is given in Eq. 1, prove to be more robust than a PID in the presence of
367 factors such as noise, which is quite common in industrial systems and real-
368 world control engineering applications. Given that control theory is out of
369 the scope of this work, the reader is referred to [50, 51] for more details about
370 the development of Eq. 1.

$$C(s) = K_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_I \cdot s} \right), \quad (1)$$

371 where C is the controller, K_p is the proportional gain, T_I [s] is the integral
372 time, and s is the variable of the Laplace domain. The units of K_p depend
373 on the units of the inputs and outputs of the system, and C has the same
374 units as K_p (see Table 3).
375

376 2.4. Performance parameters

377 The key parameters calculated in this work to characterize the perfor-
378 mance of the commercial MD system are the permeate flux ($PFlux$) and the
379 specific thermal energy consumption ($STEC$), which are the most frequently
380 reported in the MD literature.

381 $PFlux$ [$Lh^{-1}m^{-2}$] is given by Eq. 2 and represents the permeate flow
 382 rate produced per m^2 of membrane area. Its intensive nature facilitates the
 383 comparison between MD systems.

$$PFlux = \frac{PFR}{A}, \quad (2)$$

384 where A [m^2] is the membrane area and PFR [Lh^{-1}] is the permeate flow
 385 rate, calculated directly from the permeate volume produced per operational
 386 time.
 387

388 The parameter $STEC$ [$kWh_{th}m^{-3}$] measures the thermal energy required
 389 by the system to produce 1 m^3 permeate (Eq. 3). Given that it refers to the
 390 whole MD system and not only to the modules, this parameter also takes
 391 into account the heat losses.

$$STEC = \frac{1000 \cdot ThPower}{PFR} = \frac{FFR \cdot \rho_f \cdot Cp_f \cdot (TEI - TCO)}{3.6 \cdot 10^6 \cdot PFR}, \quad (3)$$

393 where $ThPower$ [kW_{th}] is the external thermal power supplied to the system,
 394 PFR [Lh^{-1}] is the permeate flow rate, FFR [Lh^{-1}] is the feed flow rate,
 395 TEI [$^{\circ}C$] is the evaporator channels inlet temperature, TCO [$^{\circ}C$] is the cool-
 396 ing channels outlet temperature, ρ_f [kgm^{-3}] is the density of the feed, and
 397 Cp_f [$Jkg^{-1}^{\circ}C^{-1}$] is the specific heat capacity of the feed. More information
 398 on the calculation of these two physical properties is given in Section 2.5).
 399

400 It is important to note that electrical energy represents only a minor
 401 fraction of the total energy consumed by the MD system. For this reason,
 402 the characterization performed in this work has been focused on permeate
 403 productivity and thermal energy demand, which will play a more important
 404 role in subsequent techno-economical studies.

405 2.5. Physical properties

406 Physical properties of the feed included in Eq. 3, i.e., ρ_f and Cp_f , are
 407 a function of temperature and salinity. Both have been estimated using
 408 the correlations developed by Sharqawy et al. [52], and implemented in
 409 open-source Matlab scripts available in [53].

410 2.6. Cost analysis

411 Results of a preliminary cost analysis are provided in Section 3.3 to com-
 412 plete the techno-economic assessment of the desalination unit. Concretely,

413 the levelized cost of water ($LCOW$ [$USD\ m^{-3}$]), which is the cost of pro-
 414 ducing $1\ m^3$ of freshwater, has been estimated using Eq. 4:

$$LCOW = \frac{OPEX + \alpha \cdot CAPEX}{LF}, \quad (4)$$

415
 416 where $OPEX$ [$USD\ m^{-3}$] reflects the specific operational expenditures re-
 417 lated to the size of the plant, and $CAPEX$ [$USD\ m^{-3}$] means the specific
 418 capital expenditures, which mainly cover the costs of thermal and electrical
 419 energy. Besides, LF [-] is the load factor, i.e. the fraction of annual time
 420 that the plant is in operation, and α [-] is the amortization factor, given by
 421 Eq. 5:

$$\alpha = \frac{i(1+i)^{t_{pl}}}{(1+i)^{t_{pl}} - 1}, \quad (5)$$

422
 423 where i [-] is the discount rate and t_{pl} [$year$] is the lifetime of the plant.

424 The specific $OPEX$ are divided into different items (given in $USD\ m^{-3}$)
 425 related to thermal energy ($OPEX_{th}$), electrical energy ($OPEX_{el}$), insurance
 426 ($OPEX_{ins}$), replacement and maintenance ($OPEX_{rep}$) and other services
 427 ($OPEX_{other}$), as shown in Eq. 6:

$$OPEX = OPEX_{th} + OPEX_{el} + OPEX_{ins} + OPEX_{rep} + OPEX_{other} \quad (6)$$

428 On one hand, $OPEX_{rep}$ is taken as a constant, while $OPEX_{ins}$ and
 429 $OPEX_{other}$ are expressed as a certain fraction of the specific $CAPEX$, ac-
 430 cording to [40]. Cooling is considered without cost, coming from a semi-
 431 infinite source such as the sea or a well, although the cost of the required
 432 devices is included in the specific $CAPEX$. Table 1 summarizes the values
 433 considered in this work and their references in the literature. On the other
 434 hand, the specific items of the $OPEX$ coming from thermal and electrical
 435 energy are estimated by Eqs. 7 and 8, respectively:

$$OPEX_{th} = STEC\ ThCost, \quad (7)$$

$$OPEX_{el} = SEEC\ ElCost, \quad (8)$$

436
 437 where $STEC$ [$kWh_{th}\ m^{-3}$] is a result of the experiments performed in this

438 work (see Table 4), $ThCost$ [$USD kWh_{th}^{-1}$] is the thermal energy cost,
 439 $ElCost$ [$USD kWh_{el}^{-1}$] is the electrical cost, and $SEEC$ [$kWh_{el} m^{-3}$] is the
 440 specific electrical energy consumption, whose value for this paper has been
 441 taken from performance results of an ongoing large-scale MD desalination
 442 project in which V-AGMD units similar to those used in this study are being
 443 operated [54] (see Table 1).

444 The specific $CAPEX$ is itemized in two different addends, as given by
 445 Eq. 9:

$$CAPEX = CAPEX_M + CAPEX_{other}, \quad (9)$$

446 where $CAPEX_M$ [$USD m^{-3}$] refers exclusively to the V-AGMD modules
 447 (Eq. 10) and $CAPEX_{other}$ [$USD m^{-3}$] includes accessory components, such
 448 as heat exchangers, piping, and instrumentation (Eq. 11).
 449

$$CAPEX_M = \left(\frac{M}{M_{min}} \right) \left(\frac{f_M FC_{base}}{365 PFR_{base} t_M} \right) \left(\frac{PFR_{base}}{PFR} \right)^\beta, \quad (10)$$

$$CAPEX_{other} = \left(\frac{M}{M_{min}} \right) \left(\frac{(1 - f_M) FC_{base}}{365 PFR_{base} t_M} \right) \left(\frac{PFR_{base}}{PFR} \right)^\beta. \quad (11)$$

450 In these expressions, FC_{base} [USD] and PFR_{base} [$m^3 day^{-1}$] are the cost
 451 of the facility and the permeate production, respectively, in a large-scale base
 452 case considered by Bindels et al. [40], f_M [–] is the fraction of the cost of MD
 453 modules, t_M [$year$] is the lifetime of the modules, and β [–] is an economy
 454 of scale exponent. In addition, M_{min} is the minimum number of modules
 455 required in the facility to reach PFR_{base} (which is calculated considering
 456 $PFlux = 3.1 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$, the maximum reported by Andrés-Mañas et al.
 457 [35] in AS26 modules). Finally, PFR [$m^3 day^{-1}$] is the actual permeate
 458 production with the number of modules M , calculated using Eq. 12.

$$M = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{1000 PFR_{base}}{24 PFR} \right), \quad (12)$$

459 being ceil is the ceiling function (round to the least greater integer).
 460

461 The values of the constant parameters assumed in Eqs. 4 – 12 to estimate
 462 the $LCOW$ are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Values of parameters used in Eqs. 4 – 12.

Parameter	Value	Units	Reference
LF	0.95	[–]	[55]
i	0.08	[–]	[55]
t_{pl}	15	<i>year</i>	[35]
t_M	5	<i>year</i>	[35]
FC_{base}	$2 \cdot 10^5$	<i>USD</i>	[40]
FFR_{base}	100	$m^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$	[40]
β	0.8	[–]	[56]
f_M	0.3	[–]	[35]
M_{min}	53	[–]	[35]
$ElCost$	0.07	<i>USD kWh_{el}⁻¹</i>	[57]
$SEEC$	0.8	<i>kWh_{el} m⁻³</i>	[54]
$OPEX_{rep}$	0.22	<i>USD m⁻³</i>	[40]
$OPEX_{ins}$	$0.005 \cdot CAPEX$	<i>USD m⁻³</i>	[40]
$OPEX_{other}$	$0.025 \cdot CAPEX$	<i>USD m⁻³</i>	[40]

463 3. Results and discussion

464 This section will first deal with the design, implementation and testing of
 465 the regulatory control architecture developed. Later, results of the operation
 466 of the full-scale MD unit will be presented and discussed.

467 3.1. Design, implementation, and evaluation of the regulatory control loops

468 The main variables to be controlled in the full-scale MD unit are the
 469 working flow rates FFR_1 and FFR_2 , by manipulating the frequency of each
 470 feed pump F_1 and F_2 , respectively, and the inlet temperatures TCI and
 471 TEI , by actuating in the positions of V_1 and V_2 , respectively. The dynamics
 472 of those variables were described using low-order linear models. Concretely,
 473 this approach was made with the first-order model given by the transfer
 474 function $G(s)$ in Eq. 13, due to their simplicity. For more details on system
 475 modeling based on transfer functions, the reader is referred to [50].

$$G(s) = \frac{Y(s)}{U(s)} = \frac{k}{\tau \cdot s + 1}, \quad (13)$$

476 where G is the transfer function, Y is the system output, U is the system
 477

478 input, k is the process gain, τ [s] is the time constant and s is the Laplace
 479 domain variable. The units of k depend on the units of U and Y , and G has
 480 the same units as k (see Table 2).

481 To obtain the parameters k and τ in each case, open-loop tests were
 482 performed, applying step-input changes to the setpoints of the corresponding
 483 actuators, following the methodology described in [51]. The dynamics of the
 484 experimental responses was then identified using the "System Identification
 485 Toolbox" of MATLAB. The results summarized in Table 2 show an acceptable
 486 correlation of all actuators with the first-order transfer function model.

Table 2: Experimental first-order transfer functions obtained for each control loop.

$G(s)$	$Y(s)$	$U(s)$	k	τ [s]	R^2 [%]
$G_1(s)$	FFR_1	F_1	$0.16 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \%^{-1}$	8.97	0.8290
$G_2(s)$	FFR_2	F_2	$0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \%^{-1}$	24.17	0.9143
$G_3(s)$	TCI	V_1	$0.23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \%^{-1}$	92.34	0.7245
$G_4(s)$	TEI	V_2	$0.21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \%^{-1}$	110.11	0.6878

487 In the case of pumps (with working frequencies F_1 and F_2), a first-order
 488 linear model fitted the experimental results well, with values of R^2 higher
 489 than 80 %. This suggested an approximately linear response of these actu-
 490 ators when a step input change was applied. In contrast, worse correlation
 491 coefficients were obtained in the case of G_3 and G_4 , which brought to light the
 492 nonlinear dynamics of the valves and the heat transfer in both the heating
 493 and cooling circuits.

494 Dynamic models were then used to design PI controllers for each loop.
 495 In all cases, the calculation method applied to estimate the parameters K_p
 496 and T_I (see Eq. 1) was pole-zero cancellation [50] because of its simplicity.
 497 The specifications imposed by this method are that i) the integral time of the
 498 PI controller must be equal to the time constant of the process and ii) the
 499 closed-loop time constant should be close to 80 % of that in the open loop.
 500 The controllers $C(s)$ calculated for each actuator transfer function model
 501 $G(s)$ are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameters of the controllers for each control loop.

$G(s)$	$Y(s)$	$U(s)$	$C(s)$	K_p	T_I [s]
$G_1(s)$	FFR_1	F_1	$C_1(s)$	7.64 % $h m^{-3}$	8.97
$G_2(s)$	FFR_2	F_2	$C_2(s)$	8.22 % $h m^{-3}$	24.17
$G_3(s)$	TCI	V_1	$C_3(s)$	5.32 % $^{\circ}C^{-1}$	92.34
$G_4(s)$	TEI	V_2	$C_4(s)$	5.72 % $^{\circ}C^{-1}$	110.11

502 The control loops were then tested in the full-scale MD unit. To imple-
 503 ment it, the parameters in Table 3 were introduced directly into the PLC
 504 using the programming environment *CODESYS*, fixing a sample time of 1 s.
 505 An example of the experimental responses in a test with different setpoint
 506 changes in each control loop is depicted in Figure 4.

507 The setpoint of temperature *TEI* was initially fixed at 50 $^{\circ}C$, and then
 508 increased stepwise to 60 $^{\circ}C$, the minimum required temperature established
 509 in previous pilot-scale MD studies to produce an acceptable amount of per-
 510 meate. Step changes of 5 $^{\circ}C$ were introduced in the reference of the control
 511 loop, as shown in the upper chart of Figure 4. The response of *TEI* to the
 512 new reference took at least 10 min due to limitations in the thermal power
 513 supply of the biomass boiler, but it can be observed that the feedback control
 514 eliminated the offset error, despite the intrinsic non-linearity in the dynamics
 515 of the corresponding regulation valve V_2 . Regarding the temperature *TCI*,
 516 it had a faster dynamics, and both increasing and decreasing deviations from
 517 the setpoint of 25 $^{\circ}C$ were corrected by the controller C_3 in a maximum of
 518 five minutes.

519 In the case of the feed flow rates FFR_1 and FFR_2 , the middle chart in
 520 Figure 4 shows a fast control action against step inputs to keep them around
 521 the references. However, FFR_2 did not follow its reference throughout the
 522 experimental time, which is explained by the coupling between the two con-
 523 trol loops that integrate C_1 and C_2 . The full-scale MD unit includes two
 524 feed tanks (see Figure 2) to avoid an excess of hydraulic pressure drop into
 525 the evaporation or the cooling channels of the modules. Small differences
 526 between FFR_1 and FFR_2 could cause one of the feed tanks to overflow or
 527 empty over time. Therefore, to avoid that situation, the manufacturers im-
 528 plemented an internal balance mode in the PLC by means of two ultrasonic
 529 level sensors installed at the top of the feed tanks. This control loop worked
 530 in a hierarchical position higher than that governed by C_1 and C_2 . To main-
 531 tain the same liquid level in both feed tanks, the working ratio of the pumps

Figure 4: Control results obtained in the MD unit using different inlet temperatures and feed flow rates.

532 F_1 or F_2 is conveniently increased until both levels are equal, independently
 533 of the control signals provided by C_1 or C_2 . A visual representation of this ef-
 534 fect is given in the lower chart of Figure 4. During the time intervals between
 535 110 – 120 *min* and 130 – 145 *min*, the levels in both feed tanks were unbal-
 536 anced and the balance mode acted to increase FFR_2 independently of the
 537 setpoint, until it reached a height of around 490 *mm* in the first interval and
 538 of 530 *mm* in the second interval. When levels became similar, controllers
 539 C_1 and C_2 drove the process back to the setpoint, as happened in intervals
 540 120 – 130 *min* and 145 – 160 *min*. Take into account that only FFR_2 was
 541 noticeably varied by the balance mode in the example presented in Figure
 542 4 because just the level in tank T1.1 was intentionally altered manually as
 543 part of the control system test.

544 Finally, it is worth mentioning that there was an influence on the inlet
 545 temperature TEI due to the change in the feed flow rates. As shown in
 546 Figure 5 within the interval 70 – 110 *min*, the increase in FFR_2 due to
 547 the effect of the balance mode led to a slight decrease in temperature TEI ,
 548 which is associated with that flow rate. This suggested a certain degree
 549 of coupling between these control loops. Therefore, the use of decoupling

550 control strategies should be thoroughly analyzed in future works. However,
 551 control systems designed in this study were shown to be suitable enough
 552 to keep operational variables in an acceptably close range around setpoints
 553 ($FFR \pm 0.2 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $TEI \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), thus ensuring steady-state operation
 554 of the full-scale MD unit with the heat from the biomass boiler.

Figure 5: Effect of coupling between the variations of FFR_2 due to the balance mode and the temperature TEI in a steady-state operation of the MD unit.

555 *3.2. Characterization of the performance of the MD unit*

556 To evaluate the full-scale commercial MD unit presented in this work,
 557 experiments with different values of TEI , FFR , TCI and $AbsP$ were carried
 558 out. The operating conditions used in each case and the results of $PFlux$
 559 and $STEC$ are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Experiments carried out and results of key performance parameters (*Atm* means atmospheric pressure).

<i>Exp</i> #	<i>AbsP</i> [mbar abs]	<i>TEI</i> [°C]	<i>FFR</i> [L h ⁻¹]	<i>TCI</i> [°C]	<i>S</i> [g L ⁻¹]	<i>PFlux</i> [L h ⁻¹ m ⁻²]	<i>STEC</i> [kWh _{th} m ⁻³]
1	<i>Atm</i>	60.5	3900	25.0	60.9	0.75	417
2	<i>Atm</i>	57.9	6000	25.7	64.4	1.35	435
3	<i>Atm</i>	57.1	7100	29.5	64.9	1.42	444
4	<i>Atm</i>	65.0	4000	25.0	59.1	1.10	349
5	<i>Atm</i>	62.4	6000	27.7	62.5	1.56	412
6	<i>Atm</i>	65.2	7100	29.7	63.0	1.64	433
7	<i>Atm</i>	71.2	3700	24.7	58.3	1.19	290
8	400	60.8	3900	34.5	62.1	0.82	195
9	400	65.9	3900	34.8	66.7	0.69	185
10	400	65.0	7000	40.2	66.5	0.99	336
11	400	70.2	3800	35.1	65.5	0.47	172
12	<i>Atm</i>	60.3	3900	35.0	66.4	0.62	212
13	<i>Atm</i>	65.7	3900	35.9	66.6	0.65	287
14	<i>Atm</i>	65.8	7000	41.3	66.8	1.34	288
15	<i>Atm</i>	70.5	3900	35.8	66.9	0.71	287
16	150	64.1	7000	40.0	64.1	0.86	234

560 As is well-known in the field of MD, increasing the amount of thermal
561 energy delivered into the MD modules is beneficial for the permeate pro-
562 ductivity because a larger thermal input widens the temperature difference
563 between both sides of the membrane. This leads to a larger difference in
564 the transmembrane vapor pressure, thus improving the driving force of the
565 MD process. Increasing *TEI* and *FFR* allowed enhancing the permeate pro-
566 ductivity, as shown in Figure 6 for seven experiments carried out in AGMD
567 mode (without vacuum assistance) and with temperature *TCI* between 25
568 and 30 °C.

569 Concretely, raising *TEI* from 60 to 70 °C improved *PFlux* up to 59 %
570 and reduced *STEC* around 30 %, down to 290 kWh_{th} m⁻³. In addition,
571 *PFlux* was double at *FFR* = 7000 L h⁻¹ than at *FFR* = 4000 L h⁻¹,
572 but at the expense of 20 % higher *STEC*. However, with both values of
573 *TEI* 60 and 65 °C, the improvement in *PFlux* was much more significant
574 between *FFR* values of 4000 and 6000 L h⁻¹ (experiments 1–2 and 4–5)
575 than between 6000 and 7000 L h⁻¹ (experiments 2–3 and 5–6). Although
576 the latter leap in *FFR* was smaller, the results showed a progressive loss of
577 performance and suggested that the temperature *TCI* played an important
578 role in the operation of this full-scale MD unit. Between experiments 2
579 (*TCI* = 25.7 °C) and 3 (*TCI* = 29.5 °C), increasing *FFR* for 1000 L h⁻¹
580 (200 L h⁻¹ per module) led to only 5 % of improvement in *PFlux* due to the
581 worsening of the condensation capacity, although no noticeable variations in

Figure 6: Effect of TEI and FFR on $PFlux$. $TCI = 25 - 30$ °C, AGMD operational mode. Numbers inside columns indicate the experiment (see Table 4).

582 $STEC$ were estimated. The same effect was observed between experiments
 583 5 and 6 with $TEI = 65$ °C. The maximum value of $PFlux$ attained in
 584 this AGMD operation was $1.64 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$, with $FFR = 7100 L h^{-1}$ and
 585 $TEI = 65.2$ °C (experiment 6).

586 Furthermore, a comparison of experiments with similar TCI also brought
 587 to light the importance of cooling power in MD operation. The results shown
 588 in Figure 7 evidenced that when there are limitations in cooling power, the
 589 condensation process is hampered and consequently $PFlux$ is drastically
 590 reduced, as Andrés-Mañas et al. reported in a pilot-scale VMEMD unit
 591 operated with sensible heat recovery in the condenser [36].

592 The effect of TCI on the performance was also notorious in both op-
 593 erational modes tested: AGMD and V-AGMD. Figure 7 shows the results
 594 of $PFlux$ obtained in experiments carried out at $FFR = 4000 L h^{-1}$ with
 595 different temperatures TCI in AGMD and V-AGMD modes (see Table 4).

Figure 7: Effect of TCI and the operational mode on $PFlux$. $FFR = 4000 L h^{-1}$. Numbers inside columns indicate the experiment (see Table 4).

596 Increasing TEI means a larger thermal input into the MD modules and
 597 hence a higher vapor production. Considering the AGMD experiments 1, 4,
 598 and 7 mentioned above (with TCI around $25^{\circ}C$), both $PFlux$ and $STEC$
 599 (blue columns in Figure 7 and 8) were improved. A higher amount of vapor
 600 allowed to recover more latent heat of condensation in the feed circulating
 601 along the cooling channels of the modules when $TCI = 25^{\circ}C$. This led to
 602 a reduction of 28 % in $STEC$ between experiments 1 (with $TEI = 60.5^{\circ}C$)
 603 and 7 (with $TEI = 71.2^{\circ}C$).

Figure 8: Effect of TCI and operational mode on $STEC$. $FFR = 4000 L h^{-1}$. Numbers inside columns indicate the experiment (see Table 4).

604 In contrast, the increase of TEI , especially above $60\text{ }^{\circ}C$, was not beneficial
 605 when TCI was around $35\text{ }^{\circ}C$. The increment of the thermal input with the
 606 feed led to a more intense preheating of the cooling current, which had a
 607 nonconvenient high temperature in itself. This reduced the cooling power,
 608 and therefore this increase in vapor production did not increase $PFlux$ in the
 609 AGMD mode. As shown in Figure 7, raising TCI from $25\text{ }^{\circ}C$ (blue columns)
 610 to $35\text{ }^{\circ}C$ (red columns) resulted in a loss of $PFlux$ which was greater the
 611 higher the TEI was, up to 40 % even at the lowest FFR (from $1.19 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$
 612 in experiment 7 to $0.71 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$ in experiment 15). Besides, no noticeable
 613 increase in permeate productivity was recorded with TEI when TCI was
 614 around $35\text{ }^{\circ}C$. Consequently, the values of $STEC$ worsened to 30 % since
 615 the additional thermal input did not lead to a significant improvement in
 616 $PFlux$, as shown with red columns in Figure 8 (experiments 12, 13, and 15).

617 The effect of absolute pressure on the performance of the MD unit was
 618 also assessed. Removing air from the gaps of the modules and the permeate
 619 circuit allows to reduce mass transfer resistance, speeding up the diffusion
 620 of vapor through the membrane pores. This fosters heat transfer to the feed
 621 that circulates along the cooling channels and hence the thermal efficiency.
 622 However, results in this study have shown that vacuum was actually detri-
 623 mental to $PFlux$, possibly due to a lack of cooling power. For any value of
 624 the remaining operational variables, an upper limit value of TCI must ex-

625 ist, the negative effect of which overcame the benefits of using vacuum. Bad
626 cooling could cause an excess of vapor that clogs the membrane pores and the
627 gaps, thwarting mass transfer, and hence latent heat recovery. Besides, the
628 lack of condensation could drive some vapor outside the module with the liq-
629 uid feed and through the permeate circuit, which would hamper an increase
630 in $PFlux$. In this context, Figure 7 shows that vacuum had only a beneficial
631 effect when TEI was $65\text{ }^{\circ}C$ or lower, even at the lowest FFR considered
632 ($4000\text{ }L\text{ }h^{-1}$). Thus, it seems that for $TEI = 70\text{ }^{\circ}C$ and $FFR = 4000\text{ }L\text{ }h^{-1}$,
633 a value of TCI of $35\text{ }^{\circ}C$ was too high for vacuum to have a positive effect
634 and most likely took noncondensed vapor outside the module.

635 Due to the increased TCI , the external thermal needs were lower to reach
636 TEI , which offset the reduced $PFlux$. Therefore, the increase in TEI from
637 $60\text{ }^{\circ}C$ to $70\text{ }^{\circ}C$ caused only a small decrease of $STEC$, as shown in Figure
638 8. The lowest $STEC$ value obtained in this assessment was $172\text{ }kWh_{th}\text{ }m^{-3}$,
639 corresponding to experiment 11, carried out at the highest TEI and the low-
640 est FFR considered. These conditions to maximize thermal efficiency are
641 consistent with those established in previous studies with full-scale multien-
642 velope modules similar to those installed in the unit operated for this work
643 [24, 26, 33].

644 Finally, V-AGMD operation was tested with different values of $AbsP$
645 and the highest FFR considered ($7000\text{ }L\text{ }h^{-1}$). Results in Figure 9 showed
646 that maintaining $400\text{ }mbar\text{ }abs$ inside the modules (experiment 10) reduced
647 $PFlux$ 26% compared to that obtained in experiment AGMD 14.

Figure 9: Effect of TCI and $AbsP$ on $PFlux$. $TEI = 65\text{ }^{\circ}C$, $FFR = 7000\text{ }Lh^{-1}$. Numbers inside columns indicate the experiment (see Table 4).

648 On one hand, the effect of increasing TCI up to $40\text{ }^{\circ}C$ when operating
649 in AGMD is a reduction in $PFlux$. In these conditions of limited cooling
650 capacity, vacuum was detrimental, as discussed above, and $PFlux$ decreased
651 with reducing absolute pressure in the gaps, as shown in Figure 9. Moreover,
652 reducing from 400 to 150 $mbar\ abs$ worsened $PFlux$ an additional 14 %.
653 On the other hand, the $STEC$ values represented in Figure 10 decreased in
654 AGMD as TCI increased, which is consistent with the results depicted in
655 Figure 8. However, an unexpected increment of the $STEC$ was observed in
656 the V-AGMD experiment 10, with absolute pressure of 400 $mbar\ abs$ com-
657 pared to that of AGMD experiment 14, also with TCI around $40\text{ }^{\circ}C$. Besides,
658 Figure 10 shows that reducing the pressure to 150 $mbar\ abs$ (experiment 16)
659 led to a decrease of 30 % in the $STEC$ (until $234\text{ }kWh_{th}\ m^{-3}$) in compari-
660 son with that attained in V-AGMD experiment 10, even when losing 14 %
661 of permeate productivity. The former effect is easier to explain, based on
662 the lower $PFlux$ with vacuum at this high TCI , but the fact that for the
663 minimum absolute pressure the $STEC$ was improved despite being $PFlux$
664 lower than at 400 $mbar\ abs$ is less intuitive. It could be argued that the
665 absolute pressure of 150 $mbar\ abs$ was so low that it restricted the internal
666 vapor condensation at least in part of the length of the gaps, which would
667 explain the reduction of $PFlux$ compared to the operation at 400 $mbar\ abs$.
668 The availability of latent heat would therefore be lower as a result of the

669 reduced vapor diffusion. However, this fact did not correspond to a better
 670 heat efficiency, which was confirmed by the values of the temperature dif-
 671 ference $TEI - TCO$ being unexpectedly smaller in experiment 16 than in
 672 experiment 10: $3.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ vs $5.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

673 Finally, another reason that could explain the disagreement between the
 674 results in Figure 10 is an abnormal operation of the temperature probes at
 675 pressure levels as low as 150 mbar abs , rarely used in V-AGMD. It is possible
 676 that, at these low absolute pressures, the fraction of vapor in the currents is
 677 too high for such probes, which are designed to measure the temperature of
 678 liquids. As a matter of fact, precise temperature measurements are critical
 679 in the assessment of V-AGMD. When operating in conditions that maxi-
 680 mize heat recovery, the difference $TEI - TCO$ is reduced and the influence
 681 of measurement errors on the uncertainty of the estimation of key perfor-
 682 mance parameters such as $STEC$ can be huge, as shown by the error bars of
 683 Figure 10, calculated considering $\pm 0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in TEI and TCO . Therefore, the
 684 quality of temperature measurements is a matter that should be further dis-
 685 cussed in subsequent studies of pilot-scale V-AGMD because it plays a major
 686 role in the control of the process and in the techno-economical evaluation and
 687 optimization of the technology.

Figure 10: Effect of TCI and $AbsP$ on $STEC$. $TEI = 65\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $FFR = 7000\text{ L h}^{-1}$.
 Numbers inside columns indicate the experiment (see Table 4).

688 3.3. Estimation of the levelized cost of water

689 The equations presented in Section 2.6 and the constants summarized in
 690 Table 1 have been used to estimate the *LCOW* of a large-scale V-AGMD
 691 plant in two different cases among those performed in this work: case 1 (ex-
 692 periment 6), with the highest permeate productivity ($PFlux = 1.64 L h^{-1} m^{-2}$),
 693 and case 2 (experiment 11), with the highest thermal efficiency ($STEC =$
 694 $172 kWh_{th} m^{-3}$). In addition, two different costs of thermal energy have
 695 been considered for comparison: $ThCost = 0 USD kWh_{th}^{-1}$, which is the
 696 case of waste heat as in this paper, and $ThCost = 0.025 USD kWh_{th}^{-1}$,
 697 which is a reference cost of solar thermal energy produced on a large scale
 698 [57]. Figure 11 shows the results of specific *OPEX* and *LCOW* obtained.

Figure 11: Results of specific OPEX (left) and LCOW (right) for cases 1 and 2 (experiments 6 and 11 in Table 4, respectively), considering two different values of $ThCost$.

699 Using waste heat ($ThCost = 0 \text{ USD kWh}_{th}^{-1}$), the specific *OPEX* in
700 Figure 11left was reduced to 0.3 USD m^{-3} , which is a competitive value in
701 the treatment of RO brines [58]. In cases 1 and 2, the specific *OPEX* con-
702 tributed to around 50 % of the cost of freshwater production, although the
703 value of *LCOW* for case 2 was approximately 80 % higher than that of case
704 1, as shown in Figure 11right. Due to the trade-off between heat recovery
705 and freshwater production in spiral wound modules [24], increasing thermal
706 efficiency leads to a reduction in permeate productivity. Therefore, a larger
707 number of modules must be operated in case 2 to reach the production ca-
708 pacity established, which increases the specific *CAPEX* and thus negatively
709 affects *LCOW*. This confirms that operating with conditions that maximize
710 the permeate productivity (high *TEI* and high *FFR*) is the most convenient
711 strategy in a scenario in which thermal energy is free of charge.

712 In contrast, when the thermal energy production cost is included in the
713 analysis, it is mandatory to maximize the thermal efficiency of the V-AGMD
714 operation to make the operation feasible. The lowest *LCOW* obtained in case
715 2 (with minimum *STEC*) was 5.4 USD m^{-3} , 55 % lower than that of case 1
716 (with maximum *PFlux*). Moreover, the contribution of the specific *OPEX*
717 increased substantially from 50 % to 93 %, even after assuming a notorious
718 increase in the specific *CAPEX* to balance out the reduction of permeate
719 productivity per module. As shown in Figure 11 right, *LCOW* increased 24
720 times in case 1, and 6 times in case 2, compared to those calculated when
721 waste heat was supplied, and even when considering a competitive value of
722 $ThCost = 0.025 \text{ USD kWh}_{th}^{-1}$.

723 4. Conclusions

724 As part of the tasks within the AgroConnect project, carried out in the fa-
725 cilities of the IFAPA Research Center, close to the University of Almería (SE
726 of Spain), this document includes the evaluation of the largest commercial-
727 scale V-AGMD unit operated to date for the production of freshwater from
728 a concentrated brine. A simple direct control architecture based on PI con-
729 trollers was initially designed and tested to maintain steady-state operating
730 conditions of temperature and feed flow rate that the experiments required.
731 Despite the non-linearities of the actuators, especially that of the regulation
732 valve in the heating circuit, the closed-loop operation with the PI controllers
733 and feedback allowed dimming the disturbances and complement between
734 variables, keeping the process variables in steady state with deviations lower

735 than 10 % with respect to the setpoints of TEI and FFR fixed for each
736 experiment. In addition, a control loop with higher hierarchy than the previ-
737 ous was implemented to balance the level in the two feed tanks, which were
738 used as buffers to avoid an excessive hydraulic pressure drop inside the MD
739 modules. Although the balance mode behavior was satisfactory, a coupling
740 between the hot temperature and the feed flow rate was observed, which
741 brought to light the need to develop and implement more advanced control
742 architectures, including decoupling algorithms that improve the accuracy and
743 velocity of the control system even more.

744 Controlling the operational variables allowed for steady-state experiments
745 to characterize the performance of the full-scale MD unit when treating a
746 real brine. Concretely, the permeate productivity and the specific thermal
747 energy consumption were the key performance parameters estimated in the
748 concentration of a real residual brine with 63.7 g L^{-1} TDS coming from an RO
749 unit at IFAPA. Operation with and without vacuum assistance was carried
750 out using five spiral wound multienvelope AGMD modules with 25.92 m^2
751 membrane area each and arranged in parallel. Another important point of
752 interest of the facility is the use of heat from a biomass boiler as thermal
753 source, which was installed as a source of CO_2 , driving the fume gases to the
754 IFAPA experimental greenhouse to be used by crops.

755 The experimental campaign carried out with the full-scale MD unit showed
756 that the inlet temperature of the cooling channels TCI was a limiting vari-
757 able, especially when operating with vacuum assistance, since it is related
758 to the cooling capacity inside the system. Operating conditions that pro-
759 mote the diffusion of vapor through the membrane pores require increasing
760 the cooling power to prevent the internal accumulation of vapor. According
761 to this, increasing TEI and FFR was beneficial to $PFlux$ only when TCI
762 was lower than $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Higher TCI values did not produce a noticeable in-
763 crease in $PFlux$ even when going up from $TEI = 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $TEI = 70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
764 The maximum $PFlux$ obtained was $1.64 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ under the conditions of
765 $FFR = 7100 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ and $TEI = 65.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

766 Moreover, results showed that reducing the absolute pressure inside the
767 gaps of the MD modules down to 150 mbar abs worsened $PFlux$ up to 40 %
768 when TCI was around $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, when compared to the same experiment car-
769 ried out in conventional AGMD. This fact brought to light that the cooling
770 limitation can cancel the beneficial effect of vacuum assistance on vapor dif-
771 fusion. The lowest $STEC$ obtained was $172 \text{ kWh}_{th} \text{ m}^{-3}$, in conditions of
772 maximum TEI ($70.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), minimum FFR (3800 L h^{-1}), $TCI = 30.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and

773 $AbsP = 400 \text{ mbar abs}$, which allowed to keep $PFlux = 0.47 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ with
774 that TCI .

775 In any case, from a technical point of view, operation with internal ac-
776 cumulation of water vapor is not convenient because of the potential risk of
777 damage on the membranes and the channels of the modules. Due to that, a
778 sufficient cooling source is mandatory for the MD operation in general and for
779 V-AGMD in particular. Apart from conventional chillers, further discussion
780 should be made in future works about the use of cheaper cooling sources with
781 semi-infinite volume, or systems supplying heat and cooling simultaneously,
782 such as heat pumps.

783 With regard to thermal supply, the techno-economic advantage of working
784 with waste heat and the importance of maximizing the thermal efficiency of
785 the V-AGMD system have been highlighted in this work. A cost analysis
786 performed with experimental results has shown that operational expenditures
787 can represent up to 93 % of the resulting $LCOW$ in a full-scale MD plant with
788 permeate capacity $100 \text{ m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$, even when the supply of thermal energy
789 at a competitive cost of $0.025 \text{ USD kWh}_{th}^{-1}$ was considered. The $LCOW$
790 estimated for the brine treatment carried out in this study was 5.4 USD m^{-3} ,
791 although this figure can be further reduced below 1 USD m^{-3} using waste
792 heat as thermal source, taken free of charge. However, given that waste heat
793 is not commonly available, future tasks in this and other related projects
794 will also consider the use of solar collectors as the main thermal source due
795 to the geographical coincidence of freshwater demand and the availability of
796 solar energy in the Mediterranean basin [59, 60], keeping the biomass boiler
797 as a supplementary unit to work all day. The implementation of cooling
798 circuits coupled to semi-infinite water sources or heat pumps must be also
799 taken into account to improve the thermal performance of the V-AGMD unit
800 and maintain the operational expenditures at an affordable level. Despite
801 all these future challenges, the results in this assessment were promising
802 enough to simply consider a thorough modeling, validation, and real-time
803 techno-economic optimization of the brine concentration system in a wider
804 operational range, with the final goal of integrating it into a sustainable
805 water grid that could supply water for the intensive greenhouse agricultural
806 activity of the region.

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815 **Nomenclature**

Roman symbols

A	Membrane area	m^2
$AbsP$	Absolute pressure	$mbar\ abs$
C	Controller	Same as K_p
$CAPEX$	Capital expenditures	$USD\ m^{-3}$
C_p	Specific heat capacity	$J\ kg^{-1}\ ^\circ C^{-1}$
$ElCost$	Electrical energy cost	$USD\ kWh_{el}^{-1}$
f	Cost fraction	—
F	Working ratio of a feed pump	—
FC	Facility cost	USD
FFR	Feed flow rate	$L\ h^{-1}$
G	Transfer function of a process	Same as k
GOR	Gained output ratio	—
i	Discount rate	—
k	Gain of a process	Units of Y over U
K_p	Proportional gain of a controller	Inverse of k
$LCOW$	Levelized cost of water	$USD\ m^{-3}$
LF	Load factor	—
M	Number of modules	—
$OPEX$	Operational expenditures	$USD\ m^{-3}$
$PFlux$	Permeate flux	$L\ h^{-1}\ m^{-2}$
PFR	Permeate flow rate	$L\ h^{-1}$
R^2	Coefficient of determination	—
s	Laplace complex variable	—
S	Salinity	$g\ L^{-1}$

Continuation of *Roman symbols*

<i>SEEC</i>	Specific electrical energy consumption	$kWh_{el} m^{-3}$
<i>STEC</i>	Specific thermal energy consumption	$kWh_{th} m^{-3}$
<i>t</i>	Life time	<i>year</i>
<i>TCI</i>	Cooling channels inlet temperature	$^{\circ}C$
<i>TCO</i>	Cooling channels outlet temperature	$^{\circ}C$
<i>TEI</i>	Evaporation channels inlet temperature	$^{\circ}C$
<i>TEO</i>	Evaporation channels outlet temperature	$^{\circ}C$
<i>ThCost</i>	Thermal energy cost	$USD kWh_{th}^{-1}$
<i>ThPower</i>	Thermal power	kW_{th}
<i>T_I</i>	Integral time of a controller	<i>s</i>
<i>U</i>	System input	Several
<i>V</i>	Aperture ratio of a regulatory valve	—
<i>Y</i>	System output	Several

Greek symbols

α	Amortization factor	—
β	Scale exponent	—
ρ	Density	$kg m^{-3}$
τ	Time constant of a process	<i>s</i>

Acronyms

AGMD	Air-gap membrane distillation
AS26	Multi-envelope module with 26 m^2 membrane area
Exp	Experiment
HX	Heat exchanger
LS	Level sensor
MD	Membrane distillation
PE	Polyethylene
PI	Proportional Integral
PID	Proportional, Integral and Derivative
PGMD	Permeate-gap membrane distillation
PLC	Programmable logic controller
PP	Polypropylene
RO	Reverse osmosis
TDS	Total dissolved solids

Continuation of *Acronyms*

V-AGMD	Vacuum-assisted air-gap membrane distillation
VMEMD	Vacuum multi-effect membrane distillation

Subscripts

<i>Base</i>	Base case
<i>el</i>	Electrical
<i>f</i>	Feed
<i>ins</i>	Insurance
<i>M</i>	Modules
<i>min</i>	Minimum
<i>other</i>	Other elements
<i>pl</i>	Plant
<i>rep</i>	Replacement
<i>th</i>	Thermal

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